

Dielectric relaxation of dioxane-water mixtures using time domain technique

K. S. Kanse^a, S. D. Chavan^a, A. C. Kumbharkhane^{a*} and S. C. Mehrotra^b

^aSchool of Physical Sciences, Swami Ramanand Teerth Marathwada University,
Nanded-431 606, Maharashtra, India

E-mail : akumbharkhane@yahoo.co.in

^bDepartment of Computer Sciences and Information Technology, Dr. B. A. M. University,
Aurangabad-431 004, Maharashtra, India

Manuscript received 24 December 2004, revised 25 July 2005, accepted 26 October 2005

Abstract : The complex permittivity of dioxane in water mixtures for various concentration and temperatures have been measured as a function of frequency between 10 MHz to 20 GHz using time domain reflectometry technique. Dielectric relaxation parameters i.e. static dielectric constant and relaxation time were obtained from the complex permittivity spectra using the nonlinear least square fit method. The relaxation behaviour of these mixtures are explained by the Debye model. The Debye relaxation time of the mixture shows a maxima for the mixture with 40% of water by volume. This suggests that the tendency to form cluster between water and dioxane molecules is maximum for this mixture. The Kirkwood correlation factor, excess permittivity and Bruggeman factor have been determined at various concentration of water in dioxane.

Keywords : Dielectric permittivity, spectroscopy, mixed solvent, Kirkwood correlation.

Many dielectric relaxation studies have been reported on water¹⁻⁵, in order to investigate the hydrogen bond structure and dynamical behaviour of water. The water molecule has a permanent dipole moment, and its principal dielectric relaxation time is observed as the Debye type¹⁻⁵. When an organic compound is mixed with water, the relaxation time are changed, because the relaxation time are related to the water structure in the mixture^{2,6,7}.

Considerable dielectric relaxation studies has been done in this laboratory on binary mixtures of water with some organic polar liquids⁶⁻⁸, using Time Domain Reflectometry (TDR) technique. The relaxation time of water is increased for a particular mole fraction of water in aqueous solutions^{2,6,7}.

Dielectric relaxation studies of water in non-polar solute provide interesting information of solute-solvent molecular interaction. However, dioxane has been found to be a special interest, because it is completely miscible with water. Non-polar dioxane is useful solvent and has a very large application in industries, agricultural and biochemical intermediate.

Mashimo *et al.* have reported dielectric relaxation measurements on dioxane-water mixtures². The dielectric relaxation experiments were performed over the fre-

quency range 0.1-10 GHz, using time domain reflectometry technique. The studies suggested that, the water cluster are broken step by step by adding dioxane, and these water molecules form a micel-like clusters with dioxane molecules². Most of them are larger than the water clusters. Accordingly, the observed relaxation is larger than that for pure water. This suggest that addition of dioxane to water breaks the water structure which disappears at a critical composition².

In this work we reports the dielectric relaxation study of dioxane-water mixtures over a wide concentration ($0 < X_{iv} < 1.0$) and different temperature using time domain reflectometry technique in the frequency range of 10 MHz to 20 GHz. The static dielectric constant, relaxation time, Kirkwood correlation factors and Bruggeman factor for aqueous dioxane have been determined.

Experimental

Materials :

1,4-Dioxane was used S.d. Fine-Chem Limited, whereas water was used after double glass distillation and deionization. The solutions were prepared by mixing the dioxane and water in volume.

The dielectric relaxation of water-dioxane mixtures

were studied using Time Domain Reflectometry (TDR)^{6,7}. The Hewlett Packard HP54750 sampling oscilloscope with HP54754A TDR plug in module has been used. A fast rising step voltage pulse of about 40 ps rise time was propagated through a coaxial line system. SMA sample cell with 3.5 mm outer diameter and 1.35 mm effective pin length was used. All measurements were done under open load condition. The time window chosen for the measurements was kept at 5n sec. The change in reflected pulse shape due to the sample were monitored by sampling oscilloscope. The pulse reflected through the sample [$R_X(t)$] was compared with the reflected pulse without sample $R_1(t)$. These reflected pulses were added $p(t) = R_1(t) + R_X(t)$ and subtracted $p(t) = R_1(t) - R_X(t)$ for fourier transformation as well as data processing⁷⁻⁹. The complex permittivity spectra was obtained from reflection coefficient spectra by applying the least squares fit method as described in our earlier publications⁶⁻⁹.

Results and discussion

To evaluate various dielectric parameters, the complex permittivity $\epsilon^*(\omega)$ data were fitted by the non-linear least square fit method to the Havriliak Negami expression¹⁰.

$$\epsilon^*(\omega) = \epsilon_\infty + \frac{(\epsilon_0 - \epsilon_\infty)}{[1 + (j\omega\tau)^{1-\alpha}]^\beta} \quad (1)$$

with ϵ_0 , ϵ_∞ , τ , α and β as fitting parameters. The equation includes the Cole-Cole ($\beta = 1$), Davidson-Cole ($\alpha = 0$) and Debye ($\alpha = 0$, $\beta = 1$) relaxation models¹. In the fitting procedure, ϵ_∞ is not fitted and assumed to be 3.0. This is done because the data are not sensitive to

ϵ_∞ in the frequency range under consideration. The resulting values of dielectric relaxation parameters for dioxane-water mixtures at different temperatures are listed in Table 1.

In dioxane-water system, the dielectric relaxation can be described by Debye model under experimental error¹. The errors in the last significant digits are indicated in parentheses along with the parameters. Variation of the static permittivity ϵ_0 as a function of water concentration is shown in Fig. 1, along with literature values² reported at 20 °C. The values are in agreement with the earlier time domain work of Mashimo *et al.*². The static permittivity decreases with concentration of dioxane.

The variation of relaxation time (τ) as a function of water concentration is shown in Fig. 2 along with the literature values reported earlier² for comparison at 20°C. The relaxation time increases strongly up to 40% dioxane-water and then converges to the relaxation time by water with increasing water concentration. Similar

Fig. 1. Static dielectric constant for dioxane-water mixtures along with literature value : (◆) 15 °C (Experimental), (■) 20 °C (Yagihara).

Table 1. Temperature dependent dielectric relaxation parameters for dioxane-water mixtures

V_w	15 °C		25 °C		35 °C	
	ϵ_0	τ (ps)	ϵ_0	τ (ps)	ϵ_0	τ (ps)
0.00	83.50 (10)	9.30 (17)	78.54 (10)	8.80 (16)	73.00 (00)	6.50 (00)
0.20	52.52 (36)	19.40 (12)	49.24 (74)	18.02 (35)	47.73 (23)	11.66 (83)
0.30	41.72 (51)	26.05 (22)	40.62 (83)	26.66 (37)	37.78 (24)	17.18 (29)
0.40	32.30 (64)	31.64 (37)	33.89 (10)	39.17 (60)	29.00 (25)	20.92 (15)
0.50	24.73 (71)	37.29 (56)	22.47 (39)	30.63 (33)	21.29 (21)	22.65 (19)
0.60	17.45 (45)	37.29 (56)	15.57 (17)	29.12 (21)	15.41 (15)	22.26 (18)
0.70	11.57 (16)	36.51 (17)	10.59 (50)	18.30 (40)	9.18 (11)	17.02 (28)
0.80	8.39 (34)	34.52 (10)	7.65 (15)	16.14 (79)	7.31 (90)	17.77 (29)
0.90	5.36 (28)	30.00 (59)	5.30 (15)	16.64 (22)	4.66 (40)	7.75 (28)
1.00	2.16 (00)	-	2.26 (00)	-	2.42 (00)	-

Number in bracket denotes uncertainties in the last significant digits obtained by the least squares fit method. For example 83.50 (10) means 83.5 ± 0.1 . The realistic errors in the values is about 2% considering other experimental aspect.

Fig. 2. Relaxation time for dioxane-water mixtures along with the literature value : (♦) 25 °C (Experimental), (■) 20 °C (Yagihara).

behaviour was observed by Mashimo *et al.*². Relaxation times obtained from our measurements for dioxane-water mixtures are higher than, those reported in the literature². The difference in values may be due to method of calibration in the experimental measurement, along with the uncertainties in the measurement. However, the trend in variation of dielectric parameter with concentrations is very similar.

The dioxane-water mixture represents one of the more complicated binary systems as it has an associating component (water) plus a second component (dioxane), which is capable of forming hydrogen bonds with first components. These hydrogen bonds are believed to be strong enough to disrupt the normal water structure. The contribution of hydrogen bonds to the dielectric properties of the mixture is studied in terms of the excess static dielectric constant. The excess dielectric permittivity (ϵ_0)^E can be written as^{6,7}

$$(\epsilon_0)^E = (\epsilon_0)_M - [(\epsilon_0)_W X_w + (\epsilon_0)_D (1 - X_w)] \quad (2)$$

where the subscripts *M*, *W* and *D* represent mixture, water and dioxane, respectively, and *X_w* represent mole fraction of water in dioxane. The plot of excess permittivity

Fig. 3. The temperature dependent excess dielectric permittivity versus mole fraction water in dioxane : (Δ) 35 °C, (■) 25 °C, (♦) 15 °C.

at different temperatures vs the mole fraction of dioxane in water solutions is shown in Fig. 3. The negative values of excess permittivity suggest that the addition of dioxane to water may create multimeric structure leading to decrease in the total permittivity. The pronounced minima is found at particular concentration of water, as temperature decreases. This behaviour is attributed to the formation of cluster between unlike molecules through very strong interactions, probably a hydrogen bonding network.

In associating molecules, the molecular relaxation time is greatly influenced by intra and intermolecular hydrogen bonding¹. The departure of the Kirkwood-correlation factor *g* from unity is a measure of the extent of intermolecular hydrogen bonding. For pure liquids the Kirkwood factor can be determined by using the Kirkwood-Frohlich equation^{1,11}.

$$\frac{4\pi N\mu^2\rho}{9kTM} g = \frac{(\epsilon_0 - \epsilon_\infty)(2\epsilon_0 + \epsilon_\infty)}{\epsilon_0(\epsilon_\infty + 2)^2} \quad (3)$$

where μ is the permanent dipole moment, ρ is the density, *M* is the molecular weight, *N* is Avogadro's number and *kT* has the usual meaning. To calculate *g* we have taken ϵ_∞ values from refractive index data¹² at 25 °C. For mixtures one can not determine the values of Kirkwood factor by using the Kirkwood-Frohlich equation without any assumption.

We have assumed that the mixture can be represented by one Kirkwood correlation factor g^{eff} as^{11,12}.

$$\frac{4\pi N}{9kT} \left[\frac{\mu_w^2 \rho_w V_w}{M_w} + \frac{\mu_D^2 \rho_D (1 - V_w)}{M_D} \right] g^{\text{eff}} = \frac{(\epsilon_0 - \epsilon_\infty)_m (2\epsilon_0 + \epsilon_\infty)_m}{\epsilon_{0m} (\epsilon_{\infty m} + 2)^2} \quad (4)$$

where μ_w and μ_D are the dipole moments of water and dioxane, respectively, at 25 °C and ρ_w and ρ_D are corresponding densities. Here *V_w* is the volume fraction of water in dioxane. The values of g^{eff} are given in Table 2. It can be seen from Table 2, that for dioxane g^{eff} is unity and there is a slow increase in the values of g^{eff} in the water rich region. This suggest that adding a small amount of dioxane to water there is increased the molecular order of water.

The static permittivity ϵ_{0m} , ϵ_{0w} and ϵ_{0D} of the mixture, water and dioxane can be related with Bruggeman

mixture formula with volume fraction of water¹³. The Bruggeman's mixture formula is given by the expression¹³.

$$f_B = [\epsilon_{0m} - \epsilon_{0w}/\epsilon_{0D} - \epsilon_{0w}] / [\epsilon_{0D}/\epsilon_{0m}]^{1/3} = 1 - X_A \quad (5)$$

Bruggeman equation predicted a linear relationship between f_B and the volume fraction of X_A of water in dioxane as shown in Fig. 4. The experimental values of f_B shows non-linear behaviour (Fig. 4). We suggest modification in the Bruggeman equation as follows :

$$f_B = 1 - [a - (a - 1)X_A] X_A \quad (6)$$

where a is an arbitrary parameter, the value of $a = 1$, corresponds to an ideal mixture with no additional in-

Fig. 4. Bruggeman dielectric factor (f_B) vs volume fraction of water (X_A) in dioxane at 15 °C. Solid line represent theoretical curve according to the Bruggeman model (eq. 5) : (♦) Experimental, (■) Theoretical.

Table 2. Kirkwood correlation factor g^{eff} for dioxane-water mixtures at 25 °C

V_w	g^{eff}
0.00	1.06 (22)
0.10	1.17 (08)
0.20	1.02 (06)
0.30	1.03 (06)
0.40	1.21 (07)
0.50	1.46 (08)
0.60	1.89 (11)
0.70	1.99 (12)
0.80	2.15 (13)
1.00	2.84 (17)

Number in brackets denote errors in least significant digits by assuming 2% errors in the values of ϵ_0 and ϵ_{∞} .

teraction between dioxane and water and leads to the Bruggeman eq. (5). In Fig. 4, solid line represents curve according to Bruggeman eq. (5). The modified Bruggeman equation fits the experimental values within 2% error. The value of a has been determined by least squares fit method and found to be 1.35 in dioxane-water mixtures.

Conclusions :

The complex permittivity, static dielectric constant and relaxation time for dioxane-water mixtures have been determined at different concentrations using Time Domain Reflectometry technique (TDR). The Kirkwood correlation factor suggests that dioxane molecules interact such that the dipole have a tendency to remain antiparallel. The values of excess permittivity and Bruggeman parameter confirms that the intermolecular hydrogen bonding vary significantly with the increase in concentration of dioxane in aqueous solutions.

Acknowledgement

Necessary facilities provided by the Department of Physics, Dr. B. A. M. University, Aurangabad and School of Physical Sciences, S. R. T. M. University, Nanded are thankfully acknowledged. The financial support from the Department of Science and Technology, New Delhi is thankfully acknowledged.

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